

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation
in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Tools on the avoided damages and benefits per demo

Deliverable 3.4

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Description
TADF	TransformAr Avoided Damaged Framework
TADA	TransformAr Avoided Damaged Application
DSS	Decision Support System
WP	Work Package
CEI	Choice Experiment for Investors
URB	Urban runoff system
CAF	Crowdsourcing Citizen app
ICW	Integrated Constructed Wetlands
ICWM	Integrated Constructed Wetlands Monitoring
GB	Green Bonds
NBS	Nature-Based Solution
AF	Local Adaptation Fund
NUDG	Nudging
MRM	Mussel-Raft Monitoring
INTERM	Intertidal monitoring
RI	Resilience Index
INSUR	Insurance scheme
SCS	Smart Climate Stations
CAE	Citizen App Engagement
AWAR	Awareness-raising modules
CIH	Climate Innovation Hub
SG	Smart Grid and gates
COAST	Coastal contract
DSI	Demand analysis for social Services/Infrastructures
DB	Database
CEI	Choice experiment

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current deliverable is type “Other” and this document is functioning as a summary presentation of two main elements of Task 3.3 - Analysis of avoided damages and other direct benefits of pathways at demonstrator scale:

1. The TransformAr Avoided Damages Framework (TADF)
2. The TransformAr Avoided Damages web-based Application (TADA)

The TADF includes and integrates the steps that demonstrators followed in order to decide the climate hazards of interest, the solutions that address them and a way to quantify the effectiveness via the calculation of KPIs before and after the implementation of the solution. On the other hand, TADA is a web-based application that functions as a presentation of tools and solutions used for the TransformAr project, and at the same time as potential replicator to find the most relevant solution based on a multicriteria selection.

D3.4 serves as an information baseline to communicate on the project impacts, support policy making, and serve as a basis for Task 3.4. Moreover, the experience and knowledge gained from the demonstrators, will be used to produce a guideline of good practices, to disseminate results and render them usable and useful in other cases (D3.5).

As a follow-up to the recommendations received in the context of the second project review (February 2025), the document was restructured complementary to D3.5. D3.4 is focusing on the methodologies developed to assess the avoided damages, whereas D3.5 focuses on the application and best practices. As such, another method was developed to tackle the problem of data availability (sparse data approach) and make a stronger connection with WP2 more obvious. As a result, the avoided damages assessment can follow a data intensive approach (High data availability approach – KPIs) or a simplified approach whereas the effectiveness of solutions and high level changes in the climate condition of the futures are needed. Both methods end with the same type and format of results for consistency and have been integrated in the web application final version (due end of the project).

Introduction

In the current deliverable, the TransformAR Avoided Damages Framework (TADF) and the TransformAR Avoided Damages web-based application (TADA) are presented for evaluating and assessing effectiveness or avoided damages of the adaptation pathways produced in Task 3.2 per demonstrator.

The term *Avoided Damages* could have different interpretations depending on the context. However, in general terms, it refers to taking measures or actions to prevent or minimize damage from occurring hazards. In the existing literature there is absence of an “Avoided damages” approach. The general approach is the cost-benefit analysis of adaptation efforts, based mainly on the economic impact (losses), by the various hazards. The majority of the approaches applied to date are focused on the post-disaster analysis and adaptation of disasters, without prevention planning and analysis of the potential associated economic and environmental hazards. An attempt, similar to the approach of TADF, of a pre-disaster framework is published by UNESCO¹. In addition, Valverde, M. J., et al., 2022² proposed an avoided damages due to floods that are directly correlated to climate change and it is aiming to bridge the gap between pre- and post-hazards assessment. More precise, a series of suggested steps, from defining the cost of inaction to monetize the adaptation costs, are presented, alongside the cases of Austria and France. As it is stated, the data of aforementioned cases cannot extrapolated to European level.

In the context of the TransformAR project and *Task 3.3 - Analysis of avoided damages and other direct benefits of pathways at demonstrator scale*, Avoided Damages are the quantification of potential effectiveness of solutions implemented at demonstrator level to cope with climate change risks. The solutions have been proposed by the demonstrators of the TransformAR project during the compilation of the proposal and have been discussed and agreed upon with stakeholders during the demonstrators’ workshops (Task 3.2). The adaptation pathways defined in Task 3.2 were derived to be elaborated in the context of Avoided Damages and utilizing the tools and data compiled in WP2 to estimate the effectiveness of the solutions. Towards the latter, the TADF was compiled and applied to the demonstrators.

In addition, TADA works as a presentation of tools used by the demonstrators, their descriptions and the presentation of results of the solution using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)³ via an online interface. Moreover, a multicriteria function is accommodating possible replicators to find information on the project impacts at demonstrator level, and the most relevant solutions for their region / hazard / type of solution. The good practices and guidelines for avoiding damages and other direct costs in regional governance scale will be derived from TADA and described in D3.5.

¹ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000384487>

² Valverde, M. J., et al., 2022, Costs of adaptation vs costs of inaction

³ Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are measurable values that organizations use to assess the success or effectiveness of specific actions, processes, or strategies. KPIs help monitoring progress, identify areas for improvement, and evaluate the overall performance of an action.

TransformAr Avoided Damage Framework

Overall concept and method

In the context of the TransformAr project, the concept of Damages and Avoid Damages from climate change is developed and defined based on the current literature. As such, **damages** from climate change encompass a broad range of adverse impacts that are not adequately mitigated or adapted to, while **avoided damages** represent the benefits of effective mitigation and adaptation efforts, preventing potential future impacts. Following the definitions, an assessment framework was introduced that provides generalized quantification of avoided damages. The framework is based on estimating the current situation (baseline) and the potential effectiveness of solutions implemented at demonstrator level to cope with climate change impacts. The difference between the baseline and the effectiveness of the solutions describes the level of the damages that have been avoided. The same can be applied for the future climate scenarios, thus, estimating the avoided damages from climate change. Important and noted is that the framework needs to be applied for each climate stressor / hazard separately. In addition, to accommodate the potential lack of available data, two version of the approach is introduced; (i) High data availability - KPI based approach and (ii) Sparse data – High level approach (see Section below). For both cases, the impact quantification can be extracted via tools and models from WP2 or by expected estimation from experts. The expert input can be a percentage estimation of the amount of change in the KPI used, based on their experience, knowledge, literature review or best practices.

It is noted, that in D3.5, that concerns the good practices and guidelines for avoiding damages and other direct costs in regional governance scale, will include an update of TADF based on the TADA data and TransformAr Demonstrators feedback during the implementation. The updated version will be based on the feedback from implementing in the demonstrators of TransformAr and incorporating the knowledge, tools and data from WP2.

Figure 2.1 Avoided damages High data and sparse data availability approaches.

High data availability - KPI based approach

Methodology

The demonstrators of TransformAr were very diverse in terms of climate stressors / climate hazards, sector impacted, regional properties and solution implemented. To deliver a generalized and easy to replicate avoided damaged framework, the core element of the assessment is an extensive list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In ANNEX A: Application per demo, the implementation of the framework per hazard and the data gathered from the demonstrators of the TransformAr are presented, whereas in ANNEX B: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS presents a series of KPIs that demonstrators and replicators can choose from. The potential user of the framework should:

- Estimate the climate stressors / climate hazards that are relevant for the region under study
- Choose the KPIs that are relevant to:
 - the region
 - the potential solutions
 - the categories of impact under study
 - the data that are available or can be provided

The KPIs are grouped into 5 categories of impacts:

- Physical
- Social
- Environmental
- Health
- Economics

KPI quantification can be derived from models, datasets available at the regional or national level, expert opinion, and sensors (e.g., Internet of Things (IoT) devices). In the case of TransformAr, sensor solutions, locally available information, and datasets (provided by WP2) were amended by models.

The impacts that have been quantified via the KPIs are the basis to estimate the damages in three categories:

- **Direct damages:** Includes the Physical impacts
- **Indirect damages:** Consist of Economic and Environmental impacts
- **People damages:** Represents the Health and Social Impacts

In order to group the impacts into damages' categories, the estimated KP_1, \dots, KP_n for each category, are scaled to $KP_n \in \{0,1\}$ and the importance of each one is assessed. The latter is accomplished with the end-user opinion together with expert consulting. The importance is depicted in a scale between 1 and 5, thus, for each KP_n a scoring is correlated a_n where $a_n \in \{1,5\}$. Then, the damage is estimated as follows:

$$D = \sum_1^n \left(\frac{a_n}{5} \times KP_n \right) \quad \text{Formula 2.1}$$

In Figure 2.2, the overall process is illustrated, from the KPIs estimation to direct, indirect and People damages.

It is important that the method to quantify and assess the damages assumes that **all the KPIs have the same trend**. The latter means that either the increase translates to more damage and the decrease to less damage. As **it is not always the case**, the scaled KPIs that follow the opposite trend are adjusted as follows:

$$KPI_{adjusted} = 1 - KPI_{scaled} \quad \text{Formula 2.2}$$

In this work the positive trend is associated with increased damage. For example, in the case of the **KPI: Percentage of population with access to improved sanitation facilities/ People using safely managed sanitation services** based on the future projection the access to sanitation is decreasing. Thus, to adapt this value to show a positive trend and consequently increasing damage, the used Formula 3.2, above.

Figure 2.2 Avoided damages framework.

Sparse data – High level approach

Accurate and timely evaluations of potential climate-related risks are fundamental for the development and implementation of effective adaptation and resilience strategies, ensuring the sustainability and success of EU initiatives in the face of a changing climate. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) provides the essential scientific foundation for understanding and evaluating these risks⁴. On the other hand, global frameworks like the IPCC provide overarching principles for climate risk assessment, the specific context of projects within the European Union necessitates the integration of regional data and methodologies. In addition, at that level the data tend to be sparse or hard to get putting another barrier to applying different frameworks. The current section is to present a high-level methodological approach for avoided damages assessment, particularly in situations characterized by sparse data availability.

⁴ CLIMATE CHANGE 2023 – IPCC, https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_FullVolume.pdf

Methodology

Damage estimation

The methodology initially presented for this EU project delivery aligns with the well-established IPCC risk assessment framework, which defines climate risk as a function of the interaction between hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.

$$Risk = Hazard \times Exposure \times Vulnerability \quad \text{Formula 2.3}$$

This fundamental framework serves as the central organizing principle for understanding and evaluating climate risks in the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6)⁵. While the core equation remains consistent, AR6 emphasizes a more integrated and systemic understanding of these components and their interactions. Also, it underscores a crucial finding: for any given level of global warming, the assessed climate-related risks are higher than those reported in previous assessments, such as AR5. This indicates an increased urgency and potential severity of climate risks, suggesting a need for a more cautious approach in the risk assessment process. In the current approach, it builds on the aforementioned definition of risk and provides a way to assess damages.

$$D_{direct} = NumOfEvents \times Intensity \times \frac{Level\ of\ Damage}{\frac{NumOfEvents}{Intensity}} \times Risk\ Index \quad \text{Formula 2.4}$$

The direct damages function provides a basic structure for estimating the direct harm caused by climate-related events. This approach reflects the latest scientific understanding based on a review of recent climate econometrics literature published after 2017 via review reports⁶. One notable trend in recent research is the increasing recognition of the limitations of relying solely on local temperature data to predict physical damage⁷. Several studies argue for the inclusion of global temperature shocks, as they appear to be stronger predictors of extreme weather events that lead to substantial economic losses. For instance, research by Bilal and Känzig (2024) found that a 1°C rise in global temperature has a significantly larger negative impact on world GDP than previously estimated using local temperature variations⁸. This suggests that the current methodology should consider incorporating or at least acknowledging the findings of such studies, as relying solely on local event frequency and intensity might underestimate the broader economic risks associated with climate change.

Furthermore, the development of more comprehensive damage functions that extend beyond simply considering mean temperature changes are under development. These advanced models incorporate

⁵ www.ipcc.ch, https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_LongerReport.pdf

⁶ Network for Greening the Financial System - Acute physical impacts from climate change and monetary policy, August 2024, https://www.ngfs.net/system/files/import/ngfs/medias/documents/ngfs_acute_physical_impacts_from_climate_change_and_monetary_policy.pdf

⁷ Adrien Bilal and Diego R. Känzig, "The Macroeconomic Impact of Climate Change: Global vs. Local Temperature", NBER Working Paper No. 32450, May 2024, Revised November 2024

⁸ Senne Aerts Livio Stracca Agnieszka Trzcinska, "Economic losses from climate change are probably larger than you think: New NGFS scenarios", Centre for Economic Policy Research (CEPR), 22 Oct 2024

a wider range of climate variables, such as temperature variability, annual precipitation levels, the number of wet days, and the frequency and intensity of extreme daily rainfall⁹. The new damage function developed by Kotz et al. (2024) for the Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS) exemplifies this trend by including multiple climate impact drivers and considering the persistent effects of climate shocks over time. Incorporating such a multi-faceted approach into the direct damage model could lead to a more accurate and holistic assessment of the potential harm from climate change within the EU project.

$$D_{indirect} = D_{direct} \times 0.4 + (NumOfEvents \times \frac{Level\ of\ Damage}{NumOfEvents} \times Risk\ Index^2) \quad \text{Formula 2.5}$$

The indirect damages formula provides a way to calculate mainly economic damage, aiming to account for both direct asset losses (represented by 40% of the direct damage) and systemic economic impacts. The formula was based on a literature review on the macroeconomic impacts of climate change, published since the reference year of 2014¹⁰. This review reveals a complex and evolving understanding of the economic consequences of climate change. The fixed factor of 40% attributed to direct asset losses warrants careful examination. It is important to determine whether this figure remains a widely accepted or adequately supported estimate in more recent economic literature. More recent studies offer updated and often more granular analyses of economic losses, suggesting that a single, fixed percentage might not accurately reflect the heterogeneity of these impacts. For the purpose of TransformAr project the value of 0.4 was kept fixed.

The second term in the damage formula attempts to account for systemic economic impacts. It is noted that relies on a squared risk index, that might be too simplistic to adequately capture complex dynamic of systemic impacts. The Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS) macroeconomic modeling handbook discusses the limitations of highly aggregated models and stresses the need for models that can account for sectoral developments and the intricate interactions between climate change and economic activity¹¹. Furthermore, the delayed effects of climate shocks can persist for several years, thus, the methodology for modeling systemic indirect (economic) impacts could benefit from incorporating more sophisticated approaches 16.

$$D_{people} = \frac{Population}{1M} \times NumOfEvents \times \frac{Level\ of\ Damage}{NumOfEvents} \times Risk\ Index \quad \text{Formula 2.6}$$

⁹ Waidelich P, Batibeniz F, Rising J, Kikstra JS, Seneviratne SI. Climate damage projections beyond annual temperature. Nat Clim Chang. 2024;14(6):592-599. doi: 10.1038/s41558-024-01990-8. Epub 2024 Apr 17. PMID: 39372375; PMCID: PMC11446829.

¹⁰ IPCC, 2022: Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, 3056 pp., doi:10.1017/9781009325844.

¹¹ Network for Greening the Financial System - Climate macroeconomic modelling handbook, October 2024, https://www.ngfs.net/system/files/import/ngfs/medias/documents/ngfs_climate-macroeconomic-modelling-handbook.pdf

The provided formula for people damages aims to quantify the health costs and social disruption per capita resulting from climate-related events. As before, the formula relies on a review of publications from the World Health Organization (WHO) on climate change, as well as broader literature on quantifying the economic costs of health impacts^{12 13 14 15}. It is noted the concept of social disruption extends beyond direct health costs to include other significant impacts such as forced displacement, adverse effects on mental health, and disproportionate burdens on vulnerable populations. The current formula, which primarily focuses on a per capita calculation involving population, events, and a risk index, does not capture these dimensions of social damage, but it is an adequate approach to assess them with sparse data.

Damage Reduction

To incorporate the TransformAr solution with the current approach, efficiency factors for damage reduction are used, following cost-benefit analysis standards and referencing the Green Climate Fund (GCF) Investment Criteria (2021). The GCF's guiding document is now its Strategic Plan 2024-2027, which emphasizes cost-benefit analysis, and a paradigm shift towards climate resilience and low-carbon development¹⁶. The application of efficiency factors should be linked to measures contributing to this shift. GCF investment criteria include indicators for impact, paradigm shift, and sustainable development potential, which should be considered when determining efficiency factors. In the case of TransformAr, the efficiency factors were determined either by data series available before or after the solution implementation, or by expert opinion consultations.

Avoided damages estimation

In the previous sections two ways to estimate damages in three categories were presented. To apply the latter workflow into avoided damages, the assessment needs to be performed in comparison between two states.

- a. Baseline (Bs): Represents the current situation with current climate condition.
- b. Climate Change (CC): Represents the future following a climate scenario.

The states are assessed for two cases in the Baseline scenario and one for the Climate Change scenario:

- i. No Solution implementation (nS): It is assessed for the Baseline scenario as a representation of the current situation (ground truth) and the climate future scenarios

¹² WMO, State of the Global Climate 2024, No. 1368, https://wmo.int/sites/default/files/2025-03/WMO-1368-2024_en.pdf

¹³ SGRCP, 2016: The Impacts of Climate Change on Human Health in the United States: A Scientific Assessment. Crimmins, A., J. Balbus, J.L. Gamble, C.B. Beard, J.E. Bell, D. Dodgen, R.J. Eisen, N. Fann, M.D. Hawkins, S.C. Herring, L. Jantarasami, D.M. Mills, S. Saha, M.C. Sarofim, J. Trtanj, and L. Ziska, Eds. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC, 312 pp. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7930/J0R49NQX>

¹⁴ <https://www.epa.gov/climate-indicators/health-society>

¹⁵ EPA. 2021. Climate Change and Social Vulnerability in the United States: A Focus on Six Impacts. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, EPA 430-R-21-003

¹⁶ Investment framework | Green Climate Fund, <https://www.greenclimate.fund/projects/investment-framework>

- ii. Solution implementation (S): It is assessed for the Baseline Climate Change scenarios and defines the score of the solution in different context.

Depending on what avoided damaged the end-user wants to estimate the two stages can be estimated

- A. Short-term: It describes the immediate avoided damages the end-user has, in the current climate conditions by implementing adaptation measures.
- B. Long-term: It describes the avoided damages the end-user has for future climate conditions by implementing adaptation measures now.

The difference between the damages of the two states for either short-term or long-term, represents what can be avoided, hence, the avoided damages. Table 3.1 summarizes the cases and formulas to assess avoided damages from climate change.

Table 3.1 Formulas to assess Avoided Damages from Climate Changes.

	Baseline (now)	Future (CC)
No Solution implementation	$D_{Bs}^{nS} = f(\text{direct, indirect, people})$	$D_{CC}^{nS} = f(\text{direct, indirect, people})$
With Solution implementation	$D_{Bs}^S = g(\text{direct, indirect, people})$	$D_{CC}^S = g(\text{direct, indirect, people})$
Avoided damages	$AD_{Bs} = \frac{D_{Bs}^{nS} - D_{Bs}^S}{D_{Bs}^{nS}}$	$AD_{CC} = \frac{D_{Bs}^{nS} - D_{CC}^S}{D_{Bs}^{nS}}$
<i>nS: no Solution S: Solutions Bs: Baseline CC: Climate Change D: Damages AD: Avoided Damages</i>		

The relation between the two stages of avoided damages is expected to differ depending on the climate scenario under consideration. It is certain that as long as the climate change accelerates, the difference between immediate gains and future ones becomes bigger. Figure 2.3 illustrates the relation between the stages and two different climate scenarios; (i) mitigate climate change (RCP4.5), (ii) business as usual (RCP8.5).

Figure 2.3 Qualitatively expected relation between Short-term and Long-term avoided damages.

TransformAr Avoided Damage Application

The TADF presented in the previous sections, is applied to the demonstrators (Municipality Of Egaleo and Gjovik) and the data gathered were compiled and utilized to create TransformAr avoided damage application (TADA), (i) a web-based application that functions as a presentation of TADF approach used by the demonstrators, their descriptions and the presentation of results of the solution, (ii) a python code that accommodates the application of sparse data approach.

High data availability - KPI based approach web app

TADA can potentially be used as a Decision Support System (DSS) to support the avoided damages framework for potential replicators, policy makers and communicate the project impacts.

TADA is based on a multi-criteria method tailored to the needs and transformation pathways adopted by each demonstrator. It takes into account the geographic location and specific climate conditions and risks of each demonstrator, the sectors affected by these risks, the actionable solutions adapted by them. The interface has been developed in order to help users beyond TransformAr:

1. To learn what solutions and tools have been used to assess avoided damages in the project
2. To communicate the project impacts and effectiveness of solutions, and support policy making
3. To facilitate users with multi-criteria decisions of solution for their cases.

In the case of (3), TADA helps the user to follow a series of choices (decide what filters are relevant to their case) that present with the relevant and effective solutions already tested from TransformAr demonstrators. For each solution, the way it was assessed and information on how it can be further replicated, alongside the outcomes from applying TADF will be available in D3.5. TADA can be found at: https://mssg.ipta.demokritos.gr/transformar_tools_repo/

Figure 3.1 TADA workflow

Figure 3.2 TADA main page.

Dashboard / Services / KPIs / Overview

KPIs Overview

Hazard: ----- Environment Type: ----- Solution: -----
 Impact: ----- Category: -----

Show 10 entries Search: Search KPIs...

ID	Demonstrator	Environment	Hazard	Solution	Impact	Category	Name
1	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Flooding	Choice experiment (CEI)	Economy	Inflation	GDP deflator
2	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Water quality	Choice experiment (CEI)	Economy	Inflation	GDP deflator
3	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Flooding	Choice experiment (CEI)	Social	Economic Growth	GDP Growth Contributi
4	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Flooding	Choice experiment (CEI)	Economy	Economic Growth	GDP Growth Contributi
5	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Water quality	SWMM	Physical / Infrastructure	Human needs satisfaction	Safe sanitation access
6	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Flooding	SWMM	Physical / Infrastructure	Human needs satisfaction	Safe sanitation access
7	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Flooding	SWMM	Social	Human needs satisfaction	Safe sanitation access
8	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Water quality	SWMM	Social	Human needs satisfaction	Safe sanitation access
9	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Water quality	URB, SWMM	Physical / Infrastructure	Human needs satisfaction	Drinking water access
10	City of Lappeenranta	Urban	Flooding	URB, SWMM	Physical / Infrastructure	Human needs satisfaction	Drinking water access

Showing 1 to 10 of 348 entries Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 35 Next

Figure 3.3 TADA multi-criteria interface.

Select KPIs

*** Select from the list below the KPIs you believe will help monitor the solution you proposed.

Name	Impact	Category
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Physical / Infrastructure	Climate Hazards
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Environmental	Climate Hazards
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Health	Climate Hazards
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Economy	Climate Hazards

Next

Questionnaire

32.
Effect in the lake water pollution caused by flooding

Demonstrator: City of Lappeenranta **Environment:** Urban **Hazard:** Increased rainfall
Solution: URB, SWMM **Impact:** Physical / Infrastructure **Category:** Climate Hazards

Trend: Min: Max: Now (no solution): Now (with solution): Future (with solution):

Min

33.
Effect in the lake water pollution caused by flooding

Demonstrator: City of Lappeenranta **Environment:** Urban **Hazard:** Increased rainfall
Solution: URB, SWMM **Impact:** Environmental **Category:** Climate Hazards

Trend: Min: Max: Now (no solution): Now (with solution): Future (with solution):

Min

34.

Figure 3.4 TADA, High availability approach.

The main application comprises of two parts. The multicriteria section on the left, where the user can choose the type of hazard, type of environment, and applied solution. In addition to that, the application allows the user to import new data to the database. Based on the multicriteria selection, the results are presented on the right-hand section on the app. The results comprise of:

- Impact category
- KPI category
- KPI name
- KPI definition
- KPI equation/source

Sparse data – High level approach code

For the sparse data case, a python code has been developed that can be utilized in order to apply the TADF with small data availability. The code with a dummy dataset can be found in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15324264> (Karozis, S., & Zarikos, I. (2025). Avoided Damages estimation in Climate Resilience concept - High level approach (0.5). Zenodo.) In addition, the code was integrate in the updated version of the TADA.

HISTORICAL DATA		
Average annual extreme events	Intensity index (1-5 scale)	Area population
8.2	1.5	2100000.0
Total area size	Climate risk index (0-1 scale)	
15000	0.67	
FUTURE SCENARIOS (Low Emissions)		
Projected annual events	Projected intensity	Population change factor
9.5	1.8	0.15
FUTURE SCENARIOS (High Emissions)		
Projected annual events	Projected intensity	Population change factor
12.1	2.4	0.18
SOLUTION EFFICIENCY		
Reduction in direct damages	Reduction in indirect damages	Reduction in people damages
0.35	0.25	0.4
DAMAGE FACTORS		

Figure 3.5 TADA, Sparse data approach.

Integration in TransformAr and beyond

The current deliverable serves as a summary presentation of two essential components of Task 3.3 - Analysis of avoided damages and other direct benefits of pathways at the demonstrator scale.

The TransformAr Avoided Damages Framework (TADF) is a framework encompasses the steps undertaken by demonstrators to identify climate hazards, select appropriate solutions, and quantify their effectiveness through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) before and after implementation.

The TransformAr Avoided Damages web-based Application (TADA) *serves as both a showcase of tools and solutions utilized in the TransformAr project and a potential replicator, allowing users to find relevant solutions based on a multicriteria selection process.*

Under the TransformAr project, TADF and TADA will provide a comprehensive and replicable workflow to estimate the effectiveness of the solutions implemented during the project. At the same time, they will function as DB for all solutions and best practices of the TransformAr project, that will help potential replicators to choose and assess their solution beyond TransformAr.

ANNEX A: Application per demo

Annex A presents the available solutions and the linked KPIs for each impact category for each case study (shown in Section 2).

Municipality of Egaleo

Heatwaves

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category		Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)		Global Climate Risk Index	GDP deflator
		GDP Growth Contribution		Fire Weather Index	Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)
	Increased integration of RES	Unemployment Rate	Reduced emissions	Air Quality Index	Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)
	Global Climate Risk Index	Increased integration of RES	Global Climate Risk Index	Health impacts of exposure to noise from transport	GDP Growth Contribution
	Fire Weather Index	Global Climate Risk Index	Fire Weather Index	Mortality Rate	Production-based CO2 intensity, energy-related CO2 per capita
	Safe sanitation access	Fire Weather Index	Air Quality Index	Life expectancy rates	Unemployment Rate
	Resilience Index	Mortality Rate	Air pollution	Quality of health services	Reduced emissions
	Risk exposure	Quality of health services	Resilience Index	Death rate	Increased integration of RES
	Access to energy	Death rate	Risk exposure	Air pollution	Global Climate Risk Index
		Safe sanitation access		Healthy life expectancy	Fire Weather Index

		Healthy life expectancy		Resilience Index	Health impacts of exposure to noise from transport
		Resilience Index		Risk exposure	Resilience Index
		Local risk perception			Risk exposure
		Risk exposure			Access to energy
		Risk perception			
Solution	Climate Innovation Hub				
	Demand analysis for social services/infrastructures (DSI)				
	Smart climate stations (SCS)				
	Citizen app (CAE)				
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Guadeloupe Archipelago

Drought

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category		GDP Growth Contribution			
		Unemployment Rate			
	Global Climate Risk Index	Import value index		Global Climate Risk Index	GDP Growth Contribution
	Water stress level	GDP per capita	Global Climate Risk Index	Water stress level	Unemployment Rate
	Safe sanitation access	Global Climate Risk Index		Drinking water access	Import value index
	Drinking water access	Water stress level			GDP per capita
		Safe sanitation access			Global Climate Risk Index
		Drinking water access			
			Risk perception		
Solution	Adaptation Fund (AF)				
	Nudging (NUDG)	Nudging (NUDG)		Nudging (NUDG)	
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Coastal erosion

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Global Climate Risk Index	GDP Growth Contribution Unemployment Rate Import value index GDP per capita Global Climate Risk Index Risk perception	Global Climate Risk Index	Global Climate Risk Index	GDP Growth Contribution Unemployment Rate Import value index GDP per capita Global Climate Risk Index
Solution	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF) Nudging (NUDG)	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Flood

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Global Climate Risk Index Water stress level Safe sanitation	GDP Growth Contribution Unemployment Rate	Global Climate Risk Index Resilience Index	Global Climate Risk Index Water stress level	GDP Growth Contribution Unemployment Rate Import value index

	access	Import value index		Death rate	GDP per capita
	Drinking water access	GDP per capita		Drinking water access	Global Climate Risk Index
	Resilience Index	Global Climate Risk Index		Resilience Index	Resilience Index
		Water stress level			
		Death rate			
		Safe sanitation access			
		Drinking water access			
		Resilience Index			
Solution	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)
	Nudging (NUDG)	Nudging (NUDG)		Nudging (NUDG)	
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Hurricane

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Global Climate Risk Index	Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)	Global Climate Risk Index	Global Climate Risk Index	Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)

	Safe sanitation access	GDP Growth Contribution	Resilience Index	Death rate	Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)			
	Drinking water access	Unemployment Rate		Drinking water access	GDP Growth Contribution			
	Resilience Index	Import value index		Resilience Index	Resilience Index	Unemployment Rate		
		GDP per capita				Import value index		
		Global Climate Risk Index				GDP per capita		
		Death rate				Global Climate Risk Index		
		Safe sanitation access				Resilience Index		
		Drinking water access				Risk perception		
		Adaptation Fund (AF)				Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)	Adaptation Fund (AF)
		Nudging (NUDG)						
Percentage affected due to CC [%]								

Rising temperatures

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category		GDP Growth Contribution			
		Unemployment Rate			GDP Growth Contribution
	Global Climate Risk Index	Import value index		Global Climate Risk Index	Unemployment Rate
	Water stress level	GDP per capita	Global Climate Risk Index		Import value index
		Global Climate Risk Index			GDP per capita
		Water stress level			Global Climate Risk Index
		Risk perception			
Solution	Adaptation Fund (AF)				
	Nudging (NUDG)	Nudging (NUDG)		Nudging (NUDG)	
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Galicia

Aquaculture

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Global Climate Risk Index	Global Climate Risk Index	Reduced emissions	Global Climate Risk Index	Reduced emissions
	Resilience Index	Resilience Index Local risk perception	Global Climate Risk Index Resilience Index	Resilience Index	Global Climate Risk Index Resilience Index
	Risk exposure	Risk exposure	Risk exposure	Risk exposure	Risk exposure
Solution	Resilience Index (RI)	Resilience Index (RI)	Resilience Index (RI)	Resilience Index (RI)	Resilience Index (RI)
	Intertidal monitoring (INTERM)	Intertidal monitoring (INTERM)	Intertidal monitoring (INTERM)	Intertidal monitoring (INTERM)	Intertidal monitoring (INTERM)
	Mussel raft monitoring (MRM)	Mussel raft monitoring (MRM)	Mussel raft monitoring (MRM)	Mussel raft monitoring (MRM)	Mussel raft monitoring (MRM)
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Oristano

Flooding

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category		GDP Growth Contribution	Reduced emissions		Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)
	Global Climate Risk Index	Global Climate Risk Index	Global Climate Risk Index	Global Climate Risk Index	GDP Growth Contribution
	Water stress level	Water stress level	Sea surface temperature anomalies	Water stress level	Reduced emissions
	Resilience Index	Resilience Index	Resilience Index	Resilience Index	Global Climate Risk Index
	Risk exposure	Risk exposure	Risk exposure	Risk exposure	Resilience Index
			Risk perception	Risk exposure	
Solution	CAF	CAF	CAF	CAF	CAF
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Lappeenranta

Flooding

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Human needs satisfaction Behavioral Change Climate Hazards	Economic Growth Human needs satisfaction Behavioral Change	Behavioral Change Climate Hazards	Human needs satisfaction Behavioral Change Climate Hazards	Inflation Economic Growth Behavioral Change Climate Hazards
Solution	URB SWMM CAF	CEI SWMM URB CAF	URB SWMM CAF	URB SWMM CAF	CEI SWMM URB CAF
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Extreme weather events

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Vulnerability and Resilience	Vulnerability and Resilience Behavioral Change	Vulnerability and Resilience	Vulnerability and Resilience	Vulnerability and Resilience
Solution	CAF	CAF	CAF	CAF	CAF
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Increased rainfall

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Climate Hazards				
Solution	URB	URB	URB	URB	URB
	SWMM	SWMM	SWMM	SWMM	SWMM
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Deterioration of water quality

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Behavioral Change				
Solution	CAF	CAF	CAF	CAF	CAF
					SWMM
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Water quality

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Human needs satisfaction	Human needs satisfaction		Human needs satisfaction	Inflation
Solution	URB	URB		URB	
	SWMM	SWMM		SWMM	CEI
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

West Country Region

Drought

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
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KPI per category	Resource efficiency (Water)	Resource efficiency (Water)	Trade	Resource efficiency (Water)	Trade
	Behavioral Change	Behavioral Change	Carbon Footprint	Behavioral Change	Carbon Footprint
Solution	ICW	ICW	Resource efficiency (Water)	ICW	Resource efficiency (Water)
	NBS	NBS	Behavioral Change	NBS	Behavioral Change
				GB	GB
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

Flooding

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Resource efficiency (Water)	Trade	Trade	Resource efficiency (Water)	Trade
	Behavioral Change	Resource efficiency (Water)	Carbon Footprint	Behavioral Change	Carbon Footprint
Solution	ICW	Behavioral	Resource efficiency (Water)	ICW	Resource efficiency (Water)
	NBS		Behavioral Change	NBS	Behavioral Change
				GB	GB

Percentage affected due to CC [%]					
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Biodiversity loss

	Physical	Social	Environmental	Health	Economic
KPI per category	Vulnerability and resilience	Vulnerability and resilience Behavioral Change	Vulnerability and resilience Behavioral Change		Vulnerability and resilience Behavioral Change
Solution	ICW NBS	ICW NBS ICWM	ICW NBS ICWM		ICW NBS ICWM
Percentage affected due to CC [%]					

ANNEX B: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Annex B presents each KPI used in this framework to quantify the effectiveness of a single or the combination of multiple solutions.

Category	KPI Name	KPI Definition	KPI Units Formula	Indicative source (if any)
Inflation	GDP deflator	The GDP price deflator shows how much a change in GDP relies on changes in the price level.	Percentage Directly from data	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH#
Trade	Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)	Transactions in goods and services (sales, barter, and gifts) from residents to non-residents.	Percentage Directly from data	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH#
Trade	Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)	Transactions in goods and services (sales, barter, and gifts) from residents to non-residents.	Percentage Directly from data	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH#
Economic Growth	GDP Growth Contribution	Variation in total GDP Growth once the policy is implemented, compared to a no-policy scenario	Dimensionless Growth GDP (with policy) / Growth GDP (no-policy)	Based on previous indicators and applying effectiveness logic

CO2 Productivity	Production-based CO2 intensity, energy-related CO2 per capita	Production-based CO2 intensity is calculated as CO2 emissions per capita (tonnes/person). Included a	Tonnes Directly from data	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH#
Energy productivity	Renewable energy supply, % total energy supply	Renewable energy supply is calculated as a share of renewable sources in TES (expressed as percentage).	Percentage Directly from data	https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GREEN_GROWTH#
Economic Growth	Unemployment Rate	Percentage of the labour force unemployed (working-age residents without work divided by total labour force)	% of unemployment Directly from data	
Economic Growth	Import value index		Import value index Directly from data	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/TM.UVI.MRCH.XD.WD
Economic Growth	GDP per capita		Local currency Directly from data	http://wdi.worldbank.org/table/WV.1
Carbon Footprint	Reduced emissions	Variation of annual total carbon dioxide equivalent emissions from energy production, transportation and industry.	Total annual emissions (%) Directly from data	https://ghgprotocol.org/greenhouse-gas-protocol-accounting-reporting-standard-cities

Energy transition	Increased integration of RES	Variation of the share of capacity from renewable energy sources	Total RES capacity (%) Directly from data	
Land use	Deforestation rate	The total forest surface area that is cut down each year	Ha/year of forest loss Directly from data	Schokker, J., Kamilaris, A., & Karatsiolis, S. (2021). A Review on Key Performance Indicators for Climate Change. Advances and New Trends in Environmental Informatics: A Bogeyman or Saviour for the UN Sustainability Goals?, 273-292.
Climate Hazards	Global Climate Risk Index	The Global Climate Risk Index shows the level of exposure and vulnerability to extreme weather events	Number of deaths – Weight: 1/6, Number of deaths per 100,000 inhabitants – Weight: 1/3, Sum of losses in purchasing power parity (PPP) – Weight: 1/6, Losses per unit of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) – Weight: 1/3 Directly from data	Schokker, J., Kamilaris, A., & Karatsiolis, S. (2021). A Review on Key Performance Indicators for Climate Change. Advances and New Trends in Environmental Informatics: A Bogeyman or Saviour for the UN Sustainability Goals?, 273-292.
Climate Hazards	Fire Weather Index	Assess fire risk based on meteorological conditions	Based on 24-hour accumulated precipitation and daily values of air temperature, relative humidity,	https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims#c0=10&c12-operator=or&b_start=0

			and wind speed Directly from data	
Climate Hazards		Monitors trends in average sea surface temperature anomalies	T °C Directly from data	https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims#c0=10&c12-operator=or&b_start=0
Resource efficiency (Water)	Water stress level	The ability to meet a region's demand for water	Low-high ability to meet a region's demand for water Directly from data	Schokker, J., Kamilaris, A., & Karatsiolis, S. (2021). A Review on Key Performance Indicators for Climate Change. Advances and New Trends in Environmental Informatics: A Bogeyman or Saviour for the UN Sustainability Goals?, 273-292.
Pollution	Air Quality Index	Ranking of cities/countries based on annual average PM2.5 concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Annual average of PM2.5 concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) Directly from data	Schokker, J., Kamilaris, A., & Karatsiolis, S. (2021). A Review on Key Performance Indicators for Climate Change. Advances and New Trends in Environmental Informatics: A Bogeyman or Saviour for the UN Sustainability Goals?, 273-292.
Pollution	Health impacts of exposure to noise from transport	Chronic exposure to environmental noise significantly affects physical and mental health and well-being	Range and magnitude of chronic high annoyance and high sleep disturbance due to noise from transport Directly from data	https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims#c0=10&c12-operator=or&b_start=2

Health & Safety	Mortality Rate	The mortality rate is calculated by dividing the number of total deaths by the population size for a defined population or geographical area over a specified period.	Tot deaths/population Directly from data	
Health	Life expectancy rates	An indicator that can help measure a person's health in a community	Life expectancy rates Directly from data	Zare Mehrjerdi, Y., Alemzadeh, R. & Hajimoradi, A. Dynamic analysis of health-related factors with its impacts on economic growth. SN Appl. Sci. 2, 1440 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03203-1
Health	Quality of health services	Level of progress in the field of medical equipment and improvement in therapeutic methods		Zare Mehrjerdi, Y., Alemzadeh, R. & Hajimoradi, A. Dynamic analysis of health-related factors with its impacts on economic growth. SN Appl. Sci. 2, 1440 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03203-3
Health	Death rate	It is a measure that affects the population	Death rate Directly from data	Zare Mehrjerdi, Y., Alemzadeh, R. & Hajimoradi, A. Dynamic analysis of health-related factors with its impacts on economic growth. SN Appl. Sci. 2, 1440 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-03203-4
Health	Air pollution	Health impacts of air pollution: air pollutants and greenhouse gases	Years of life lost or Premature death in [Number] or [rate] Directly from data	Eurostat
Human needs satisfaction	Safe sanitation access	Percentage of population with access to improved sanitation facilities/ People using	% of population Directly from data	World Bank, 2020

		safely managed sanitation services		
Human needs satisfaction	Drinking water access	People using safely managed drinking water services) (%)	% of population Directly from data	World Bank, 2020
Human needs satisfaction	Healthy life expectancy	The indicator Healthy Life Years (HLY) at birth measures the number of years that a person at birth is still expected to live in a healthy condition. HLY is a health expectancy indicator which combines information on mortality and morbidity. The data required are the age-specific prevalence (proportions) of the population in healthy and unhealthy conditions and age-specific mortality information. A healthy condition is defined by the absence of	age-specific prevalence (proportions) of the population in healthy and unhealthy conditions and age-specific mortality information Directly from data	IHME GBD (2019); Eurostat (2020): https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tps00150/default/table?lang=en

		limitations in functioning/disability.		
Human needs satisfaction	Sufficient nourishment	Percentage of population meeting dietary energy requirements (%) calculated as reverse of prevalence of undernourishment (rescaled onto scale from 0%-100%)	Ratio Directly from data	WB WDI 2020; Eurostat SDG
Vulnerability and Resilience	Resilience Index	Data on safety and risk collected in the World Risk Poll from over 125,000 people in 121 countries. The Resilience Index is an average of 4 domains: Individual,	Survey Directly from data	World Risk Poll

		Household, Community, Society.		
Behavioral Change	Local risk perception	Perception of risk that one's local area will be affected by climate change	Survey Directly from data	
Behavioral Change	Risk exposure	A person's actual exposure to environmental hazards, such as noise or pollution.		
Behavioral Change	Risk perception	perceptions about threats through climate change and environmental catastrophes and how likely they are or will be prevented	Survey Directly from data	European Social Survey 2016; International Social Survey Programme: Environment IV - 2020; Attitudes of Europeans towards Biodiversity. Special Eurobarometer 481, 2018
Vulnerability and Resilience	Access to energy	Access to electricity, urban Access to electricity, rural	% of population Directly from data	https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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